

A Comparative Analysis Regarding Consumer Reactions Towards Cultural Appropriation Occurring in Fast Fashion Firms Vs. Luxurious Companies

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ABSTRACT

Cultural appropriation is a rapidly occurring phenomenon that negatively affects marginalized cultures around the world. Nowadays, the fashion industry is regarded as the biggest contributor to this social malpractice. The industry is largely split into two distinct parts: the fast fashion firms and the luxurious companies. Due to their highlighted difference in ideology, and the industry's overall contribution towards cultural appropriation, it is imperative to analyze the differences in consumer reactions, and the implications of these reactions on the companies. These reactions were analyzed through content analysis and a qualitative study based on responses present in social media and popular news outlets such as the New York Times. The results indicate that luxurious companies are perceived to have a higher amount of social accountability, and therefore need to better manage their production and marketing strategies.

Keywords: Culture Appropriation, Fast Fashion, Luxury Brands, Fashion Industry

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to rapid advances in social media, and the improvement of globalization, and communication, prominent companies have been placed under copious amounts of social responsibility. This social responsibility includes respecting all cultures and communities present throughout the world. Unfortunately, influential, luxurious brands have often been accused of conducting cultural appropriation numerous times throughout their company history (Sadaba, 2020). Cultural appropriation is known to the general public as “the unsuitable, unauthorized, or objectionable use of cultural elements in a context other than that of the culture by outsiders who might lack understanding and/or respect for the culture in question” (Gertner, 2019). These forms of cultural appropriation tend to have increasingly harmful effects, such as the promotion of cultural stereotypes (Said, 1985), and have the highest negative effects on marginalized, minority

cultures (Kulchyski, 1997). Marginalization of cultures is a critical issue troubling society in various forms. Thus due to the severity of the issue, the frequency of cultural appropriation occurring in various industries is alarming for the general public. However, it is impermanent to specifically examine the fashion industry, as this type of industry largely contributes to the occurrence of this significant issue.

The fashion industry is largely split into two distinct areas, a side that targets consumers desiring luxurious, extremely well-crafted products, and companies that aim for consumers in the market to buy affordable fashion (Mrad, 2020). Examples of brands that target the primary type of consumers include prominent names such as the aforementioned Dior (Antonaglia and Ducros, 2020), while companies that target the later type of customers include examples such as Zara and H&M (Gandhi, 2024). However, both types of companies have routinely engaged in culture appropriation, therefore directly contributing to the prevalence of cultural stereotypes and the various negative effects that minority cultures have to endure in their daily lives (Vezina, 2019). As displayed through the undertaken qualitative study, in the aftermath of the occurrence of an incident regarding cultural appropriation, there tends to be high amounts of backlash present on social media platforms such as X and Instagram. Furthermore, various media outlets such as The New York Times (Friedman, 2019) and the Guardian (Marriott, 2021) report on such incidents. However, this article aims to view the consumer reactions toward the occurrence of cultural appropriation. More specifically, how does a fashion company's target audience and stance in society affect the consumers' reactions to cultural appropriation in the United States of America?

When researching the differences between luxury and fast fashion brands, an impasse was discovered due to a lack of research between consumer reactions and responses toward social malpractice. Due to their differences in consumer ideology, the reactions can highly differ. For luxury brands, their targeted consumers often desire items that can act as symbols reflecting ideals such as social status and power (Tynan et al., 2010), while fast fashion consumers often want products with the ideology of "Buy it now, because it won't be here tomorrow" (Byun and Sternquist, 2012). Furthermore, the high prices of luxury brands can create meaningful bonds between customers and the brands (Ko et al, 2017). These differences in ideology can help explain the different consumer reactions toward brand malpractices such as cultural

appropriation. Due to the lack of research and information presented on this research question, a qualitative study was produced to bridge the gap present in current research.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Background on Cultural Appropriation

While the severe effects of cultural appropriation have been noted amongst many academics, the lack of comprehension found amongst the general population regarding the definition of cultural appropriation is concerning. As an example, researchers found that there is a lack of awareness revolving around the topic of culture appropriation among high school students, and this is extremely concerning as these students will soon participate in present-day society as legal adults (Kim & Song, 2020). To acknowledge this problem, this article adopts Ziff and Rao's (1997) definition of culture appropriation, which is "the taking—from a culture that is not one's own—of intellectual property, cultural expressions or artifacts, history and ways of knowledge." This is regarded as the widely perceived definition of culture appropriation, as various credible sources define the term in similar manners, for example, "the unsuitable, unauthorized, or objectionable use of cultural elements in a context other than that of the culture by outsiders who might lack understanding and/or respect for the culture in question" (Gertner, 2019). It is of the utmost importance that the meaning of the term, culture appropriation, is highlighted due to the grave amount of confusion present concerning the definition of the term, the issue of culture appropriation is often mixed with the phenomenon of culture appreciation.

As aforementioned, cultural appropriation occurs when there is a general disrespect of a culture, caused by a lack of knowledge regarding the traditional practices of the culture. However, if usage of another culture is attained after copious time spent studying and learning about the intricate details of the practices of the culture in hand, then the phenomenon is called, culture appreciation (Cruz et al, 2023). Both of these terms stem from the topic of culture mixing or culture fusion, also known to the general public as the spread of various cultural practices, and the interactions of multiple cultures (Cruz et al, 2023). In the contemporary era of advanced technology, cultural mixing takes place incessantly throughout each day. This allows both cultural appropriation and cultural appreciation to occur at a much more rapid pace than when

social media or other forms of technology were not present and widely used. Essentially, social media and other various pieces of technology allow information to be spread amongst various cultures and aid cultural mixing fusion (Salvetti, 2021), facilitating cultural appreciation and cultural appropriation.

As noted earlier, the general public is often confused between the terms culture appropriation and culture appreciation. To reduce this general uncertainty, it is important to compare examples of cultural appropriation and appreciation. In the world of luxury items, there have been many instances of cultural appropriation and cultural appreciation. A notable example is the Nike Panamanian Shoe Patterns scandal. In this particular scandal, the infamous fashion brand was accused of using cultural Panamanian patterns in its shoes without crediting the patterns' source (Jones, 2020). One of the most harmful aspects of cultural appropriation is the removal of credit to the source, therefore brands must provide credit where credit is due (Jones, 2020). On the other hand, as aforementioned cultural appreciation can also occur as an example, Gianfrance Ferre, an Italian artist and visionary behind Dior's 1998 Fall/Winter collection, drew great inspiration from India (Maorescu-Murphy, 2021). However, his actions were labeled as cultural appreciation as he conducted a great deal of research behind the cultural practices of craftsmanship in India, and it was widely regarded that he drew inspiration from Indian designs (Maorescu-Murphy, 2021). Unfortunately, the problem and issue of cultural appropriation is highly prevalent when it occurs and can induce great amounts of damage to the other culture, thus it is important to examine which industries greatly contribute to this social malpractice.

Cultural appropriation occurs in various industries including the travel industry. As an example, in the travel industry, "A growing number of critics believe destination brands in general, and tourist destinations in particular, have exploited indigenous groups for the commercial purpose of entertaining visitors" (Gertner, 2019). This directly impacts the attractiveness of a travel destination, and thus due to an increase in the influence of culture when consumers pick a destination to travel to, it can influence travel companies to exploit the culture present in the destination (Freire, 2022). This exploitation can occur in specific tourist attractions or through merchandise and souvenirs (Freire, 2022). Therefore, the travel industry contributes to culture appropriation through their actions to promote their own company.

However, it is widely noted that the fashion industry is largely responsible for the occurrence of cultural appropriation on a global scale in recent years due to many fashion brands being accused of malpractice (Kong, 2019). Due to the immense contributions of the fashion industry towards the malpractice of cultural appropriation, it is imperative to analyze the effects of the actions conducted by the firms. This led us to ask the necessary research question: How does cultural appropriation in the Fashion Industry affect consumers and firms?

RQ1: How does cultural appropriation in the Fashion Industry affect consumers and firms?

2.2 Background on the Fashion Industry

Throughout history, the fashion industry has been a driving social force that influences the general population in various manners (Hurlock, 1929). Due to increased consumption of fashion, the industry is widely regarded to be split into luxury and fast fashion brands that offer different ideologies and concepts of fashion. Luxury brands offer experiences along with products. The unveiling and packaging are extremely premium and exclusive, to make it a memorable moment that the consumers remember (Joy et al., 2014). The materials used to create the products are also known to be of the highest quality (Fuchs et al., 2013; Nieroda et al., 2018). In order to create such products, the prices of the products match the exclusivity of the actual product. The prices also act as a representation of the status symbols and prestige associated with luxurious products (Joy et al., 2014). In conclusion, the most distinguishing characteristics of luxury products are their high quality, emotional and practical value, precision and excellent craftsmanship, and ability to command premium prices.

In comparison, fast fashion products are based on current trends in the fashion industry. They are personified by sharp reactions due to low amounts of time wasted in the production and distribution process of items, thus enabling these companies to change stock rapidly depending on demand (Cachon and Swinney, 2011). In general, while luxurious products are known to last a long time due to their expert craftsmanship, fast fashion products are known to be temporary due to current trends in the industry (Sproles, 1981). Furthermore, in contrast to luxurious products, fast fashion designs are known to be low-cost, and oftentimes are meant to be replicas of

luxurious product designs (Amutelli et al., 2016). Additionally, fast fashion companies often continuously rotate and change their products due to new trends in the fashion industry, this also ensures that their design team has less time to fabricate new designs, thus their craftsmanship and quality are known to be less than those of luxury fashion designers (Cachon and Swinney, 2011). Due to the key differences in their ideologies and philosophies, it is extremely plausible that there are key differences in the amount of media exposure the two types of fashion companies receive. As aforementioned, status symbols and the desire for premium products are the primary driving forces behind purchases of luxurious products (Dreze and Nunes, 2009), meanwhile, the affordability, fast production times, and the reflection of current trends regularly attract fast fashion consumers (Bhardwaj and Fairhurst, 2010). Thus, luxurious products are seen to be unattainable, a status symbol for the top one percent (Joy et al., 2014). This trait regularly allows them to appear in the general media, and so when scandals appear for these luxurious companies, popular news outlets, and companies report them (Friedman, 2019). This leads to greater backlash on social media platforms as users are informed about the malpractice. Due to these discrepancies, it is critical to now ask the question:

RQ2: How does a fashion company's target audience and stance in society affect its consumers' reactions to cultural appropriation in the United States of America?

To conduct research and gather information, this study utilized content analysis to discover target consumer reactions in the aftermath of a brand committing cultural appropriation. The data sources include numerous scholarly articles published in prominent academic journals such as JACR related to the topic of culture appropriation in the two chosen fashion companies: Dior and Zara. Furthermore, social media and news outlets' responses to individual culture appropriation incidents occurring at Dior and Zara are also examined. These responses are utilized as a way to provide information about the differences in consumer responses for the two companies.

2.3 Company Background: Dior

Dior is considered to be a powerhouse fashion brand created by the visionary Christian Dior in 1947 (Antonaglia and Ducros, 2020). They utilize their unique and distinct connections with the art world to create 'timeless' pieces that they ensure they display (Antonaglia and Ducros, 2020).

Also, they ensure that there is a great variety to their pieces, as they produce pieces for haute couture, while also having products aimed at the general global market (Antonaglia and Ducros, 2020).

Furthermore, they market their relations to the art world by blurring the line between creative directors and artists (Antonaglia and Ducros, 2020). They want their consumers to feel like they have just purchased not only a creative artistic expression but also a product that will endure the challenges of time (Antonaglia and Ducros, 2020). Additionally, they gain media exposure through the products being seen with powerful and important females such as Princess Diana. Dior's iconic handbag, the 'Lady Dior' was the princess's choice of bag, as she purchased every color of the handbag (Rashwan). Due to this exposure, the bag rose in popularity to become one of the most well-known bags of the century (Rashwan). Due to the inspiration Dior takes from other artists and cultures around the world, it has often been brought up in the conversation about cultural appropriation and cultural appreciation. However, there have also been great accusations of cultural appropriation toward Dior.

2.4 Company Background: Zara

On the other hand, Zara is considered to be a fast fashion company based in the Galicia region of Spain (Gandhi, 2024). The founder of the company, Amancio Ortega, launched the company in 1975, with the implementation of fast fashion production, and brand expansion, Zara rose as a prominent player in the fashion industry (Gandhi, 2024). The company offers a variety of products to its consumers, such as accessories, clothing, cosmetics, swimwear, and fragrances. As aforementioned, the biggest selling point for fast fashion brands is the quick turnaround time and wide selection of offerings at an affordable price. In the case of Zara, the company designs and ships new products to its wide assortment of stores in a month (Gandhi, 2024). Furthermore, Zara manages to distribute 10,000 different products in a calendar year (Gandhi, 2024).

With these key selling points, Zara targets consumers interested in a wide assortment of products that reflect current trends at an affordable price (Gandhi, 2024). The key difference between the marketing strategies of Dior and Zara is the socio-economic condition of their targeted consumers. Due to this important factor, the overall facets of their brand that they use to attract

consumers highly vary. As mentioned before, Zara prioritizes displays of current trends, efficiency in the production process, and affordable prices to attract consumers (Cachon and Swinney, 2011). Zara utilizes these aspects to formulate their entire marketing strategy, including the advertisements and deals that they communicate to consumers.

3. DISCUSSION

3.1 Cultural Appropriation in Dior Products

Recent accusations include the infamous Savage advertisement scandal and the Chinese horse skirt scandal. In 2019, Dior was accused of cultural appropriation due to a new pleated wool, and mohair skirt that they had launched as an official product (Holland, 2022). However, the similarities of the skirt to a traditional and cultural Chinese skirt, often called a horse face skirt, were unmistakable. Originally dating back to the Song Dynasty of China, the horse skirt was designed for horse rides in ancient times, with pleats present to make their experience more comfortable (Holland, 2022). Chinese citizens felt that the skirt launched by Dior bore too many similarities to this cultural piece of clothing. However, the moment this issue emerged as a case of cultural appropriation was when Dior didn't correctly identify the influence of the traditional horse skirt on their skirt design. They communicated to their audiences that their design was a production of their artistic capabilities and was not related to the traditional Chinese horse skirt design. Their target consumers on social media didn't agree with their reasoning (Freesia, 2022).

Essentially, Chinese citizens took to social media to share their accusations that Dior's new product was a product of cultural appropriation. There was an uproar on social media platforms such as Twitter as the responses by consumers were mostly negative. Users wrote argumentative phrases such as "Stop Cultural Appropriation" (温皇诚不欺人, 2022) and highlighted their negative opinion by uttering "These behaviors are outright discrimination" (Freesia, 2022). Furthermore, the extremely negative commentary led to a protest in China against the fashion brand (Holland, 2022). The protest occurred in the streets of Paris, a location far from the country of China (Holland, 2022). This indicates strong feelings among Dior's potential consumers in a variety of targeted markets. Additionally, the social media content posted by

protesters and onlookers alike further stimulated negative discussion surrounding the act of cultural appropriation conducted by Dior.

Furthermore, Dior was once again accused of cultural appropriation due to the Sauvage advertisement scandal. 'Sauvage' was a new perfume product that Dior was aiming to launch in the year 2019, however, a teaser trailer starring Johnny Depp generated great amounts of backlash on social media platforms due to the apparent and highlighted cultural appropriation present in the short video (Friedman, 2019). In the video, Dior chose to include a native American man dancing in ceremonial clothes, while also wearing a headdress made out of feathers (Friedman, 2019). Due to the stereotypical imagery and the name of the product, which many deem to be similar to the word 'savage', the advertisement contributed to the cultural appropriation of Native Americans living in the United States (Friedman, 2019).

The response on social media platforms and media outlets was highly negative. The New York Times, a source of current events and news for many Americans and the International community, uttered a response "This is a commercial no one is ever supposed to see again" (Friedman, 2019). Similarly, users on the infamous social media platform Twitter responded by saying "Hope the person who came up with that idea loses their bonus" (Maven, 2019). Thus indicating that there were significant negative emotions directed towards the advertisement. The significant public outrage influenced Dior's decision to act.

Dior as a company limits responses to public opinion due to its image as a social status company, however, the company was forced to retract its advertisement of the Sauvage perfume (Friedman, 2019). Furthermore, the company even put out a media statement that reiterated its apologies to the general public regarding contributing to cultural appropriation in the form of aiding native american stereotypes (Friedman, 2019). However, while Dior apologized and removed the Sauvage Advertisement from all of their social media platforms, in the case of the Chinese horse skirt incident, they instead denied the similarities present between the traditional cultural Chinese horse skirt and their wool skirt. Instead, they cited school skirts as the main inspiration behind their design (Friedman, 2019).

On the other hand, the key similarity between the two incidents is the extreme media exposure they received, with numerous comments on social media and from various news outlets such as CNN, and NBC. Furthermore, both scandals negatively affected the brand image of Dior, therefore, the company viewed the scandals as potential threats to its carefully curated public image. This is displayed through the action of removing the Savage advertisement video. Thus, due to Dior's actions, it is plausible to assert that culture appropriation-based scandals negatively harm a luxurious company's public perception, which can reduce the number of target consumers.

3.2 Zara Cultural Appropriation

However, even though Dior's and Zara's marketing strategies are highly differentiated, both brands have been accused of committing cultural appropriation numerous times throughout the history of the brands. In the case of Zara, multiple news media outlets have reported numerous cases, such as the Indian Lungi Incident, and the Mexican Cultural Patterns incident. However, these two incidents had a lower amount of media exposure on social media platforms such as Twitter and other forms of media. Furthermore, in Zara's Mexican Cultural Pattern incident, many of the news media and social media backlash focused on the incident due to the response of the Mexican government (Marriott, 2021).

In this case, Zara used traditional Mexican patterns in one of their products, without giving credit to the country or where the pattern originated from (Marriott, 2021). Zara presented a new product known in the fashion industry as a midi dress, however, the issue of cultural appropriation appears due to the design of the dress. The design essentially holds remarkable similarity to a "pattern distinctive to the indigenous Mixteca community of San Juan Colorado" (Marriott, 2021). This further prompted the Cultural Minister of Mexico to send and sign a letter addressed to Zara discussing the situation (Marriott, 2021). The letter claimed that the design "reflects ancestral symbols related to the environment, history and worldview of the community" and was similar to traditional *huipil* dresses which, it said, were part of the women's identity and took local craftspeople at least a month to make" (Marriott, 2021). Thus highlighting how Zara conducted cultural appropriation as they plagiarized their designs and discredited local, indigenous designs. Furthermore, due to this official response, there was a high amount of social

media backlash present on various social media platforms. Since Zara has a higher target consumer audience as compared to Dior, it can be assumed that the consumers reacting to the situation on Zara are the brand's target consumers. Furthermore, due to the backlash present on media platforms, which included users on Twitter asking if it was socially acceptable to continue shopping at Zara, it is apparent that cultural appropriation negatively affected their targeted consumers.

Furthermore, Zara was involved in another cultural appropriation scandal appropriately named the Indian Lungi Incident. In this particular case, Zara once again presented a product that was indigenous to Indian communities, without reporting the influence the original design had on their product (Janmohamed, 2018). In short words, Zara again proceeded to plagiarize a traditional design and displayed actions of cultural appropriation. In India, a Lungi is a traditional garment for men to wear instead of trousers (Janmohamed, 2018). However, Zara has reproduced the garment to be a skirt designed for women, the similarities present between the traditional Lungi and the new skirt are alarming: the original traditional patterns of the lungi and their infamous folds are all present on Zara's new skirt (Janmohamed, 2018). Thus highlighting how Zara conducted cultural appropriation as they plagiarized their designs and discredited local, indigenous designs. Furthermore, due to this official response, there was a high amount of social media backlash present on various social media platforms.

On social media platforms and on other forms of media such as opinion articles, Zara's image deteriorated. For example, Shelina Janmohamed (2018), a news writer for the National Newspaper described the situation: "This is not ignorance. This is disrespect, entitlement, and cultural appropriation. It's the fact that cultural symbols are usurped and exoticized but the people who created them are not given credit" (Janmohamed, 2018). This demonstrates the extremely negative opinions adopted by Zara's target consumers. Furthermore, on the popular social media platform Twitter, users highlighted Zara's level of ignorance and research: "I give you the lungi-dads-skirt disaster by @ZARA where ANY Indian person could've pointed out in two minutes what the problem is with this" (Bell, 2018). This further demonstrates the almost amusing amount of ignorance present behind this example of cultural appropriation.

3.3 Summary

As described in the earlier portions, Zara and Dior have both been involved in numerous cases of cultural appropriation throughout their brand history, however, the media exposure the two brands have received heavily differ. While Dior's actions of cultural appropriation were easily identifiable, however, there was a noticeable lack of research detailing the fast fashion brand's malpractice of their social responsibility. This was also the case in academic journals, there were many articles detailing the history of cultural appropriation in luxurious companies such as Dior, Chanel, and Ralph Lauren (Green and Kaiser, 2017). However, there was an extremely limited amount of articles detailing the occurrences of cultural appropriation in fast fashion firms.

Furthermore, higher expectations for action and change after Dior had committed malpractice of their social responsibility were emphasized. For example, Dior was forced to remove their Savage advertisement after prominent backlash, however, Zara was able to continue practicing their business ideas after merely denying the influence of traditional Mexican patterns on their products. This is the effect of the increased media exposure as essentially Dior is held accountable due to the increased attention on the brands. Thus, it can be concluded that due to the increased attention and highly negative reactions from Dior's targeted consumers as compared to Zara, luxurious brands have a higher amount and magnitude of reactions as compared to fast fashion brands.

Additionally, it was found that upon the occurrence of cultural appropriation in a fast fashion company, consumers viewed the situation with a lens of humor instead of outrage. This was a stark difference when compared to the consumer reactions of luxury companies. When conducting the research method, it was observed that consumers often viewed the event of cultural appropriation occurring in a fast fashion company rather seriously, thus leading to government involvement in the response to cultural appropriation (Marriott, 2021). This further highlights how consumers tend to have higher expectations from fast fashion firms as compared to luxurious companies.

This implies that companies, specifically, luxurious companies need to embrace a higher level of caution when conducting marketing practices, and producing future products due to the higher magnitude of reactions compared to fast fashion companies. A common thread noticed in culture appropriation is the lack of credit given to the originating culture, and so if a luxurious company draws inspiration from a culture, to not initiate strong negative reactions from consumers, it needs to cite the culture as an influence in their product. Furthermore, being aware of cultural norms around the world can help reduce cultural appropriation mistakes when marketing a new product (Cruz et al, 2023).

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, after conducting research it was discovered that luxurious companies targeted consumers have higher numbers and more extreme reactions on social media and other forms of media such as opinion articles. Thus, to limit losing consumers and having extremely negative public relations, luxurious companies have to have higher amounts of social responsibility when conducting their businesses. In the modern day and age of social media, information and backlash are extremely easy to spread, therefore companies have to take caution to limit negative repercussions, however, due to the status of luxurious companies such as Dior, they have to take even more caution as their repercussions are greater in magnitude than those of fast fashion companies such as Zara.

5. LIMITATIONS

However, similarly to other research papers, the presented findings do possess limitations. Throughout the article, the research method primarily conducted a qualitative study. To undertake a deeper level of comprehension of consumer reactions, future research may apply the quantitative method to deeply examine the reactions numerically. Furthermore, this article examined two specific companies. In order to have a broader understanding, it would be imperative to analyze multiple different cases from various companies in multiple industries. The decision to examine the fashion industry was reached because the fashion industry is the biggest perpetrator in regards to the social malpractice of cultural appropriation, however as previously

discussed, industries such as the entertainment industry, and the travel industry also regularly commit acts of cultural appropriation. Thus, to generalize the thesis of the article, those industries would further need to be analyzed.

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